

MANAGING RISKS IN SMALL BUSINESSES: IMPLEMENTATIONS, CHALLENGES, AND COPING STRATEGIES AS BASIS FOR BUSINESS CONTINUITY PLAN

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Managing Risks in Small Businesses: Implementations, Challenges, and Coping Strategies as Basis for Business Continuity Plan

Jayson G. Acuna*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aims to analyze the demographic profile of small enterprises (SEs) and their level of risk management implementation in San Francisco, Agusan del Sur. Utilizing a convergent parallel method, the research involved 34 SEs for a quantitative survey and ten critical informants for qualitative interviews conducted during the academic year 2022-2023. The findings reveal that sole proprietorship is the most common business form among SEs, reflecting a preference for sole ownership, and management was primarily engaged in wholesaling as the primary business activity. Most SEs have been operating for 7 to 10 years, indicating a prevalence of mid-term established businesses, whereas fewer are in the startup phase, suggesting challenges in early business survival. Regarding risk management practices, SEs demonstrate a comprehensive and robust approach, with all indicators showing a "Fully Implemented" level. Event Identification and Monitoring are solid areas, highlighting proactive risk management efforts. Despite this, the Internal Environment, while strong, is comparatively lower. The study also identifies key challenges in implementing risk management practices across cultures. Addressing these challenges, the coping strategies are changing organizational mindsets, enhancing training, structuring framework, and ensuring communication. The duration of operation significantly influences risk management implementation, with newer enterprises needing to prioritize risk management from the start and established businesses focusing on continuous improvement. The proposed intervention plan aims to sustain risk management practices by enhancing internal environments, event identification, continuous improvement, early adoption, and knowledge sharing. By equipping SEs with the necessary knowledge, tools, and resources, the plan seeks to ensure their resilience and long-term success in a dynamic business landscape.

Keywords: *small enterprises, risk management practices, risk management implementation, challenges, coping strategies*

Introduction

Risk management is an essential process that involves identifying, evaluating, and addressing potential threats to an organization's financial health and stability. Effective risk management is crucial for maintaining sustainability and fostering growth in today's complex and unpredictable business environment. These practices enable organizations to navigate uncertainties, protect their assets, and leverage opportunities. However, many businesses, especially small enterprises, lack the resources and expertise to implement thorough risk management. Nevertheless, embracing robust risk management strategies can significantly improve an organization's resilience and long-term success. Therefore, prioritizing risk management is not just a defensive measure but a strategic imperative that can drive sustained growth and competitive advantage. The proper practice of risk management by small enterprises influences the business's performance (Apaloo S., et. al 2022). Then, several authors have highlighted the importance of risk management in small enterprises. For instance, Kenton W. (2021) emphasizes that effective risk management can significantly reduce uncertainties in investment decisions, which is particularly important for small enterprises with limited resources. While according to Nyabuti and Ombaba (2019) highlighted the importance of diversified product offerings in stabilizing SMEs' financial performance were product diversification effectively manages credit risk. In addition, Abeyrathna and Priyanath (2020) suggested that effective risk management can enhance business performance by aligning it with the owner's risk tolerance. And Toma S. et al. (2020) highlighted that a positive and significant relationship between the application of risk identification techniques, risk assessment analyses, and risk treatment methods, and the degree to which these practices are embedded in SMEs' activities.

Despite the crucial role that small enterprises played in the economy, they faced numerous challenges, with risk management being among the most pressing. Effective risk management was essential for the sustainability and growth of small enterprises (SEs). However, many SEs lacked the resources and expertise to work on this, compounding the issue as most existing research focused on larger organizations, leaving a significant gap in understanding how small enterprises could effectively manage risks. This study sought to address this gap by exploring small enterprises' current risk management practices, uncovering their specific challenges, and proposing practical strategies to enhance and sustain their risk management capabilities. By focusing on SEs, it aimed to provide practical insights and solutions that addressed their unique needs and constraints, ultimately contributing to their long-term success and resilience. Furthermore, more research needed to be explicitly conducted in San Francisco, Agusan Del Sur.

This study is significant because it aimed to understand how small enterprises managed risks, a topic often overshadowed by research on larger companies. By providing practical and affordable risk management strategies, the study sought to enhance the resilience and growth of local SEs despite their limited resources. This approach would not only stabilize and diversify the local economy but also inform policymakers in developing better support programs tailored to small businesses. Ultimately, this research empowered small

enterprises, contributing to the region's long-term economic vitality.

Research Questions

The study focuses on the risk management practices of Small Enterprises and aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the Small Enterprises in terms of:
 - 1.1. form of business;
 - 1.2. nature of business; and
 - 1.3. no. of years of operation?
2. What is the level of implementation of risk management practices among Small Enterprises in terms of:
 - 2.1. internal environment;
 - 2.2. objective setting;
 - 2.3. event identification;
 - 2.4. risk assessment;
 - 2.5. risk response;
 - 2.6. control activities;
 - 2.7. information and communication; and
 - 2.8. monitoring?
3. What are the challenges encountered in implementing the Risk Management Practices?
4. What are the coping strategies to overcome the challenges in implementing Risk Management Practices?
5. Is there a significant relationship among the respondent's profile and its level of implementation of risk management practices?
6. Based on the findings, what intervention should be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a convergent parallel design and a mixed-method approach to comprehensively understand risk management practices in small enterprises. The convergent parallel design allowed the researcher to conduct both quantitative and qualitative components concurrently, giving equal importance to each approach. By independently examining both parts and then integrating the findings, the researcher aimed to triangulate the methodologies for corroboration and validation (Creswell & Pablo-Clark, 2011).

The quantitative research approach involved gathering and analyzing numerical data to assess risk management practices among small enterprises. This was achieved through the distribution of structured survey questionnaires to a sample of small enterprises. The survey was designed to gather specific data on demographic profiles and various aspects of risk management, including internal environment, objective setting, event identification, risk assessment, risk response, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring.

Conversely, the qualitative research approach provided deeper insights into the challenges encountered in the implementation of risk management practices and the coping strategies employed by small enterprises. This was accomplished through in-depth interviews with key informants from the small enterprise sector. These interviews aimed to explore the emerging challenges and strategies related to risk management that the quantitative survey might not fully capture.

Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected simultaneously and analyzed independently within the concurrent parallel design. This design was well-suited for this study as it facilitated a balanced and thorough examination of small enterprises' risk management practices. By leveraging both methodologies, the study aimed to provide a comprehensive analysis that could inform better risk management strategies and interventions tailored to the unique needs of small enterprises.

Respondents

The research focused on the risk management practices of small enterprises (SEs) in San Francisco, Agusan del Sur. The population data, sourced from the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) upon the researcher's request, indicated 34 small enterprises. The researcher conducted a complete enumeration, meaning all 34 small enterprises were included in the study. This approach ensured a comprehensive analysis of risk management practices within this subset of enterprises. By focusing on small enterprises and employing these sampling techniques, the study aimed to provide a thorough and accurate assessment of risk management practices across different sizes of enterprises in Agusan del Sur.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Registered Small Enterprises</i>	<i>Populations</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
San Francisco	34	34

Instrument

The researchers employed an adapted survey questionnaire based on Lynn Altemeyer's (2004) study, "An Assessment of Texas State

Government Implementation of Enterprise Risk Management." This questionnaire has been customized to suit the context of Small Enterprises (SEs) in Agusan del Sur.

The research instrument consists of two main parts: Part 1 comprises the demographic profile, this section aims to gather pertinent information about the respondents, including their form of business, nature of business, and years of operation; Part 2 assesses the extent of implementation of risk management practices among SE's. It includes indicators such as internal environment, objective setting, event identification, risk assessment, risk response, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring. Respondents will rate each indicator on a Likert Scale ranging from 1 (Not Implemented) to 5 (Fully Implemented).

Moreover, the research instrument would undergo validation procedures to ensure its face and content validity. Experts representing various sectors, including academe, the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), and risk management practitioners, validated the questionnaire. Their feedback and suggestions were considered to enhance the instrument's comprehensiveness and relevance to the study context.

Then, following the validation process, the questionnaire was pilot-tested with non-respondents of the study to assess its reliability. This pilot testing phase aimed to identify any potential issues or ambiguities in the questionnaire and ensure its clarity and effectiveness in eliciting responses from the target respondents. The reliability and acceptability of the questionnaire will be further evaluated by a statistician affiliated with the university, ensuring that it produces consistent and dependable results.

Procedure

The data for this research were collected using a survey questionnaire and interviews with key informants. The procedure followed these steps:

The researcher sent permission to the panelist for the implementation of the study. Then, the researcher sent a letter to the LGU for the conduct of the research and to the respondents and secured their approval to participate in the study. Upon receiving consent from the respondents, the researcher administered the survey questionnaire. This process involved distributing the questionnaire, collecting completed forms, and ensuring the participation of all respondents. The researcher collected the completed survey questionnaires from each respondent. The data from these questionnaires were then tallied and tabulated on a prepared tabulation sheet for data presentation and analysis.

Further, the researcher sent written consent to the critical informants before conducting the interviews. The researcher used a non-directive interview style with open-ended questions, allowing the informants to control the pacing and subject matter. For clarification, a more directive style was used when necessary. The interviews were recorded with the informants' consent, and additional sub questions were asked as needed. The audio recordings were transcribed verbatim and translated into English for data analysis.

The researcher anticipated and addressed ethical considerations during the data-gathering process, ensuring the protection of participants' rights and promoting the integrity of the research. The following safeguards were implemented: voluntary participation of informants was informed in writing that their participation was voluntary, and they could withdraw at any time or decline to answer any questions without any consequences. The research objectives were clearly outlined in writing and explained to the participants. Participants were provided with written information about all data collection methods and activities. Steps were taken to monitor the collected data to ensure the safety and privacy of the participants. Written transcriptions and interpretations of the data were shared with the participants. When reporting the data, the participants' rights, interests, and wishes were given priority, and decisions regarding their privacy were made under the Data Privacy Act.

By following these procedures, the researcher aimed to collect comprehensive and reliable data while respecting the ethical considerations necessary for conducting a responsible and trustworthy study.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire were tallied, analyzed, interpreted, and summarized according to the statistical tools to be used.

Frequency, Percentage, and Ranking are the tools used to analyze and interpret the demographic profile of Small Enterprises for problem 1.

Weighted mean and standard deviation are used to analyze the implementation levels of risk management among small enterprises.

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) is used for the statement of problem no. 5 to determine whether there is a significant relationship between the respondent profile and the level of implementation of risk management practices.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the exhibition, analysis, and interpretation of the data collected in the study. Content is presented based on the order in which the problem is explained.

Demographic Profile of Small Enterprises

The data on the form of business among small enterprises reveals significant insights into their demographic profile. Sole proprietorship emerges as the most prevalent form of business, representing 53%. This suggests that many small enterprises value the principles of sole management and benefit. The popularity of sole proprietorship indicates a strong preference for sole ownership and decision-making by the owner, particularly attractive in sectors or communities where sole resources can enhance business success and sustainability.

The high frequency of sole proprietorship highlights a trend towards sole responsibility in the small enterprise sector. Sole proprietorship benefits such as sole governance flexibility and owner resource pooling may have driven this trend. In contrast, partnerships are the least common form of business among the options provided, with only 18% of small enterprises opting for this structure. This relatively low percentage may reflect a preference for more structured or collective forms of business organization, such as corporations and cooperatives, which offer different advantages regarding liability, governance, and resource pooling.

Table 2. *Demographic Profile of Small Enterprises*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Form of Business			
Sole Proprietorship	18	53%	1
Partnership	6	18%	3
Corporations	10	29%	2
Cooperative	0	0%	
Total	34		
Nature Of Business			
Manufacturing	6	18%	2
Retailing	5	15%	4
Wholesaling	18	53%	1
Service	5	15%	4
Total	34		
No. Of Years of Operation			
Below 3 years	1	3%	5
3 years to 6 years	2	6%	4
7 years to 10 years	12	35%	1
11 years to 13 years	10	29%	2
14 years and above	9	26%	3

The lesser inclination towards partnerships suggests potential challenges in finding suitable business partners or a preference for corporations' and cooperatives' perceived stability and formal structure. Overall, the data indicates that small enterprises tend to favor cooperative structures, which emphasize mutual aid, democratic governance, and collective benefit, over partnerships, which involve sole ownership and management responsibilities.

The data on the nature of business among small enterprises reveals that wholesaling is the most common, with 53% of small enterprises distributing goods to retailers or other companies. This indicates that many small enterprises find value in the intermediary role of moving products from manufacturers to the market. According to the study of Banda & Hapompwe (2023), the high percentage of wholesalers highlights the importance of this sector in the supply chain and its attractiveness to small enterprise owners who can leverage wholesale distribution for profitability and scalability.

In contrast, retailing and service businesses are the most minor typical businesses among small enterprises, representing only 15%. The relatively low dominance of retail businesses suggests that fewer small enterprises directly sell goods to consumers, possibly due to intense competition in the retail sector, making it challenging for small enterprises to establish and sustain themselves.

Similarly, the low frequency of service businesses indicates that fewer small enterprises focus on providing intangible products such as consulting, repairs, or personal services. This might be due to the specialized skills and expertise required for many service-oriented businesses, which can be a barrier to entry for some entrepreneurs. Additionally, the service industry often involves higher levels of customer interaction and personalized service, which can be resource-intensive and challenging for small enterprises to manage effectively (Banda & Hapompwe, 2023).

The data suggests that small enterprises are likelier to engage in wholesaling activities, while retailing and service businesses are less common. This trend highlights the importance of understanding the unique challenges and opportunities faced by small enterprises in different sectors to support their growth and success.

The data on the number of years of operation among small enterprises provides insights into the longevity and stability of these businesses. 7 to 10 years emerges as the most common duration for small enterprises, representing 35%. This indicates that many small businesses have reached stability and maturity, successfully navigating through the initial and often more vulnerable early years. The relatively high frequency of companies in this category suggests that many small enterprises can sustain operations and growth over a

mid-term period, showcasing the potential for small businesses to achieve and maintain stability, highlighting the importance of supporting enterprises through their critical early years to reach this stage.

However, the period of operation below three years is the least common among small enterprises, with only 3%. This low frequency indicates that only some tiny enterprises are in their initial startup phase, reflecting high barriers to entry, a challenging competitive environment, or a lack of adequate support for new companies. This finding highlights new small enterprises' challenges and the need for targeted support and resources to help them survive and grow beyond the early stages (Hopkin, 2018).

Summary of the Level of Implementation among Small Enterprises on their Risk Management Practices

The data provided includes the weighted mean and verbal descriptions for various indicators of risk management practices among small enterprises. The grand mean of 4.34 indicates that, on average, risk management practices among small enterprises are fully implemented. This suggests a comprehensive and consistent approach to managing risks across their operations.

According to Metzker et al. (2023), Ojubanire & Dawodu (2021), and Poba-Nzaou, Galani, & Aloui (2022), a robust risk management culture within small enterprises reflects a high level of adherence to established practices and frameworks. It indicates that these businesses prioritize risk management and have effectively integrated it into their organizational processes. The very high overall implementation level implies that small enterprises are likely well-prepared to handle potential risks, which can lead to improved resilience and stability.

Table 3. *Summary of the Level of Implementation among Small Enterprises on their Risk Management Practices*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Internal Environment	4.26	Fully Implemented
Objective Setting	4.35	Fully Implemented
Event Identification	4.40	Fully Implemented
Risk Assessment	4.36	Fully Implemented
Risk Response	4.39	Fully Implemented
Control Activities	4.33	Fully Implemented
Information Communication	4.29	Fully Implemented
Monitoring	4.40	Fully Implemented
Grand Mean	4.34	Fully Implemented

However, this comprehensive approach may enhance their ability to respond to adverse events, protect assets, and ensure business continuity. Additionally, it may improve stakeholder confidence, including customers, investors, and partners, by demonstrating a commitment to risk management (Metzker et al., 2023; Ojubanire & Dawodu, 2021; Poba-Nzaou et al., 2022). Overall, the data suggests that small enterprises have a robust risk management culture and are well-prepared to handle potential risks, which can lead to improved resilience and stability.

Both event identification and Monitoring have the highest weighted mean of 4.40, indicating they are fully implemented to the highest degree among all the indicators. The high event identification rating suggests that small enterprises are proficient in recognizing potential risks and opportunities, which is critical for proactive risk management. Similarly, the exceptionally high rating for Monitoring indicates that these businesses are diligent in continuously observing and evaluating their risk management processes to ensure they remain effective. Further, the study of Agbodza (2020) and Ahmed, Mukhongo, and Datche (2019) shows that the intense focus on event identification ensures that small enterprises can anticipate and prepare for potential risks before they materialize, reducing the likelihood of unforeseen disruptions. Effective Monitoring implies that these enterprises can quickly identify and address any weaknesses or inefficiencies in their risk management practices, maintaining a high standard of risk control over time. These strengths can lead to a more agile and resilient business operation.

The internal environment has the lowest weighted mean of 4.26 among the risk management indicators, though it is still described as fully implemented. While the internal climate is slightly lower than other indicators, it still signifies a strong foundation for creating an organizational culture supporting risk management. This includes factors like leadership commitment, ethical values, and organizational structure. The slightly lower score for the internal environment suggests minor areas for improvement in fostering a risk-aware culture or enhancing leadership involvement in risk management. Addressing these areas can further strengthen the overall risk management framework, ensuring that all employees are aligned with the organization's risk management objectives and that there is strong support from the management (Bilcan F, Ghibanu, Bratu, & Bilcan G, 2019; Wong et al., 2023; Thabit, 2019; Lee, 2023). Overall, the internal environment still demonstrates a high level of implementation, indicating that small enterprises have established a solid foundation for supporting their risk management practices through leadership, values, and organizational structure. However, continuous efforts to enhance the internal environment can contribute to a more robust and effective risk management system.

The Challenge in the Implementation of the Risk Management Practices of Small Enterprises

Based on the responses of the key informants to the question "What are the challenges in implementing risk management practices?". The responses of the key informants highlight one common theme and challenge in implementing risk management practices within

organizations, which emerges cultural resistance.

Cultural Resistance

Informant 1: “Organizational employees and leaders need to change their perspective on risk. A culture that pays attention to risk management needs to be implemented, but it often conflicts with traditional methods and mindsets.” (Ang mga empleyado ug lideres sa organisasyon kinahanglan nga mausab ang ilang panglantaw bahin sa risgo. Ang usa ka kultura nga maghatag ug pagtagad sa risk management kinahanglan nga ipatuman, apan kini kasagaran makalalis sa mga tradisyonal nga paagi ug mindset.)

Informant 2: “Implementing risk management requires dedicated support from top management. If leaders don't care, employees may not care about it either.” (Ang pag-implementar sa risk management nagkinahanglan ug dedikadong suporta gikan sa taas nga pamunuan. Kung ang mga lideres dili magpakabana, ang mga empleyado mahimo nga dili sab maghatag ug importansya niini.)

This suggests that a culture that supports risk management is essential for the success of risk management practices. Several studies support the theme of cultural shift and leadership support in implementing risk management practices among small enterprises. The need for a cultural shift towards risk management is highlighted because it often conflicts with traditional mindsets and methods.

The literature highlights the importance of organizational culture in nurturing a risk-aware environment. For instance, a study on the impact of risk management on the performance of small and medium enterprises amid crises found that risk identification is a crucial component of risk management practices and that robust risk identification processes positively correlate with financial resilience and improved economic performance (Aoun, 2023). Another study examining the impact of organizational culture and risk management on performance in healthcare organizations found that adequate consideration of the interaction of risk management and control systems with organizational culture is one of the best ways to prevent operational failure (Lee, 2023).

Overall, the literature supports the findings that a cultural shift toward risk management is necessary, but it often conflicts with traditional mindsets and methods. Dedicated support from top management is crucial for successful implementation, and a culture that supports risk management is essential for the success of risk management practices.

Coping Strategies implemented by Small Enterprises to overcome Challenges

Based on the key informants' responses to the question, "What are the coping strategies in implementing risk management practices?" The responses highlight several themes regarding coping strategies in implementing organizational risk management practices, including leadership support, employee training, structure frameworks, and standard communication.

Leadership Support

Informant 1: “Make leaders role models in demonstrating the importance of risk management practices.” (Himuong modelo ang mga lider sa pagpakita sa kahinungdanon sa risk management practices.)

Informant 2: “Ensure that leaders actively support and promote risk management initiatives.” (Siguraduhon nga ang mga lider aktibong nagasuporta ug nagpromote sa mga risk management initiatives.); and “Create a committee made up of senior leaders to focus on issues and initiatives related to risk management.” (Maghimo ug komite nga gilangkuban sa mga senior leaders nga mag-focus sa mga isyu ug inisyatiba nga may kalabotan sa risk management.)

This reflects the critical role of leadership in demonstrating the importance of risk management practices and actively supporting and promoting risk management initiatives among small enterprises. The study by Mamai and Kadouamai (2021) suggests that leaders demonstrating the importance of risk management can positively influence employees' adoption of these practices. The study by Moshesh, Niemann, and Kotzé (2018) emphasizes the need for leadership commitment to ensure the successful implementation of risk management initiatives.

Employee Training

Informant 1: “Conduct regular training sessions to provide awareness on the importance and processes of risk management.” (Magpatuman ug regular nga mga training sessions aron mahatagan ug kahibalo bahin sa kahinungdanon ug mga proseso sa risk management.); Informant 3 “Launch programs to raise awareness about potential risks and their impact on the business.” (Maglunsad ug mga programa aron mapataas ang awareness bahin sa mga posibleng risgo ug ang ilang epekto sa negosyo.);

Informant 4: “Provide continuing education and professional development opportunities for employees regarding risk management.” (Maghatag ug padayon nga edukasyon ug professional development opportunities para sa mga empleyado bahin sa risk management) and” Get experts or consultants to provide guidance and training.” (Magkuha ug mga eksperto o consultants aron maghatag ug guidance ug training.); and

Informant 10: “Provide adequate training to employees on the use of new technologies and tools related to risk management.” (Maghatag ug igo nga training sa mga empleyado bahin sa paggamit sa mga bag-ong teknolohiya ug tools nga may kalabotan sa risk management.).

This highlights the importance of conducting regular training sessions and awareness programs and providing continuing education

and professional development opportunities for employees to equip them with the knowledge and skills needed for effective risk management among small enterprises where the study of Yang, Ishtiaq, & Anwar (2018) suggest that providing continuing education and professional development opportunities ensures that employees stay updated with the latest risk management practices and techniques. In contrast, the study of Qubtan, Gan, Hadi, Jalil, and Rambeli (2021) found that practical risk management strategies are primarily linked to training and developing awareness about risk among SMEs.

Structured Frameworks

Informant 5: “Create a structured framework that is easy to integrate with existing business processes.” (Maghimo ug usa ka structured framework nga sayon i-integrate sa kasamtangang business processes.); “Regularly review and adjust processes to ensure risk management is integrated.” (Regular nga susihon ug i-adjust ang mga proseso aron siguraduhon nga naka-integrate ang risk management.)

This highlights the importance of creating a structured risk management framework that is easy to integrate with existing business processes among small enterprises. Regular review and framework adjustments ensure its continued relevance and effectiveness in managing risks over time. Accordingly, the study of Mthiyane, Van der Poll, and Tshehla (2022) suggests that a structured framework that aligns with existing processes is essential for successful implementation. Additionally, reviewing and adjusting processes is crucial to ensure that risk management practices remain relevant and effective over time (Turgay & Aydın, 2023; Yılmaz, 2019).

Standard Communication

Informant 3: “Create clear channels for reporting and discussing risks.” (Maghimo ug klaro nga mga channel para sa pag-report ug pagdiskusyon sa mga risgo.)

Informant 7: “Develop standard templates for risk reporting to streamline the process and avoid confusion.” (Mag-develop ug standard templates para sa risk reporting aron mapadali ang proseso ug malikayan ang kalibog.); and “Conduct regular updates and meetings to discuss risks and the steps taken to address them.” (Magpatuman ug regular nga updates ug meetings aron hisgutan ang mga risgo ug ang mga lakang nga gihimo aron masulbad kini.)

Creating clear channels for reporting and discussing risks, developing standard templates for risk reporting, and conducting regular updates and meetings to discuss risks are crucial aspects of effective risk management practices in small enterprises. Conferring from the study of Mthiyane, van der Poll, and Tshehla (2022) on risk management in small and medium enterprises emphasizes the need for clear communication channels to foster risk awareness throughout the organization and ensure successful implementation of risk management practices. Another study on the drivers of implementing risk management practices highlights the importance of effective communication channels for reporting and discussing risks to ensure that risk management efforts are well-coordinated and aligned with organizational objectives (Qubtan et al., 2021).

Significant relationship among the Small Enterprises profile and its Level of Implementation of Risk Management Practices

The p-value of 0.000 indicates a statistically significant relationship between the number of years of operation and the level of implementation of risk management practices among small enterprises. Consequently, the duration of operation significantly influences the extent to which risk management practices are implemented, with longer-operating enterprises typically having more comprehensive risk management frameworks. Additionally, newer enterprises should prioritize establishing effective risk management practices to ensure business resilience and longevity. As businesses mature, they will likely refine and enhance their risk management processes, leading to more robust risk mitigation strategies (Malik et al., 2017).

Table 4. *Significant relationship among the Small Enterprises profile and its Level of Implementation of Risk Management Practices*

	Source of Variances	p-value	Conclusion
Level of Implementation of Risk Management Practices	Form of Business	0.221	There is no significant relationship
	Nature of Business	0.073	There is no significant relationship
	No of Years of Operation	0.000	There is a significant relationship

However, the p-values of 0.221 and 0.073 for the form and nature of business, respectively, indicate no statistically significant relationship between these factors and the level of implementation of risk management practices among small enterprises. Further, for the form of business, whether a small enterprise operates as a sole proprietorship, partnership, corporation, or cooperative does not notably impact the extent to which risk management practices are implemented. Similarly, the nature of business—whether in manufacturing, retailing, wholesaling, or services—does not significantly influence risk management implementation within small enterprises. So, these findings suggest that small enterprises can choose their business structure and industry sector based on legal considerations and management preferences without significant concerns about their effects on risk management implementation. However, regardless of the chosen structure or industry, prioritizing effective risk management remains crucial for ensuring business resilience and sustainability. All small enterprises must implement robust risk management practices to identify, assess, and mitigate potential risks, regardless of the specificities of their business form or industry sector (Renault, 2018).

Conclusions

In conclusion, the analysis of small enterprises in Agusan Del Sur reveals several key findings that provide valuable insights into their business profiles and risk management practices.

Sole proprietorships are the most prevalent form of small enterprise, showing a preference for individual ownership and management, while partnerships are the least common. Wholesaling is the dominant business activity, with less frequent retail and service businesses. Most small enterprises have been in operation for 7 to 10 years, indicating a mid-term establishment, but only some are in the startup phase, highlighting challenges in early survival. Tailored support and policies are essential to assist startups and promote long-term stability.

Small enterprises demonstrate a thorough approach to risk management, with all indicators rated as "Fully Implemented." Event Identification and Monitoring are incredibly robust, and the Internal Environment indicates a strong risk management culture.

Due to the conflict between traditional methods and mindsets, small enterprises need help implementing risk management, including cultural resistance.

Proactive strategies, including leadership backing, employee training, structured frameworks, and effective communication, help to overcome these obstacles and promote long-term success.

The duration of operation significantly impacts risk management implementation. New enterprises should prioritize risk management from the outset, while established businesses should concentrate on ongoing improvement. Sharing experience and knowledge within the small enterprise community can enhance risk management practices and resilience.

The intervention plan focuses on the internal environment, event identification, continuous improvement, early adoption, and knowledge sharing to sustain risk management practices. The plan aims to empower small enterprises to navigate challenges effectively and achieve long-term success in a dynamic business landscape by providing the necessary knowledge, tools, and resources.

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, actionable recommendations are proposed for various stakeholders involved with Small Enterprises (SEs).

For SE owners, it is essential to continually review and update their risk management practices to address emerging risks and enhance operational effectiveness, especially in cultivating a risk-aware culture within these organizations, which is equally vital.

For SE investors, evaluating the risk management capabilities of potential investment targets is crucial for reducing investment risks and ensuring sustainable returns. Another critical recommendation is to provide financial and technical support to help SEs enhance their risk management capabilities. Encouraging new SEs to prioritize establishing risk management practices from the outset can mitigate risks and improve long-term success. Moreover, facilitating access to resources such as training programs and expert consultations can enhance the overall risk management infrastructure within SEs.

For the Department of Trade and Industry, the agency may consider training focused on the suggested intervention in terms of cultural awareness, practical structure framework, and information and communication to sustain the risk management of small enterprises.

For future researchers, investigating barriers to adopting risk management practices among SEs is essential for informing strategies to promote diverse business structures. Assessing the long-term effectiveness of risk management practices through longitudinal studies can refine frameworks and improve relevance over time. Exploring industry-specific risk management needs and challenges within the SE sector can lead to developing tailored strategies. Additionally, researching strategies and policies to support SEs during their startup phase can improve survival rates and contribute to economic growth. Implementing these recommendations collectively will enhance risk management practices among SE organizations, improve investment opportunities for investors, and advance research efforts in the field, ultimately contributing to the resilience and sustainability of small enterprises and the broader economy.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jayson G. Acuna

Saint Francis Xavier College – Philippines